

Ghosted Rooms: A Novel Grid-Based Puzzle with Unique Room Partitioning

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Website: <https://ghosted-rooms.com>

Abstract

Ghosted Rooms is a grid-based logic puzzle played on a grid of numbers. The grid must be partitioned into rooms, where each room is either empty or contains distinct numbers. The shapes of the rooms are fixed.

Example

Given the grid:

	1	9		5	9	8	1		5	
				4	3	1	0	7		
		2	9	7	2		5	2	3	1
5	6	6				6	9	8		
							4		2	7
		8		7	1	0		6		
8		9	2		5			7	4	
		6	4	0		7	5	0		5
8		5		4	3	8				
2		1	0	6	1	6	7			

And the possible room shapes (rotations and reflections allowed):

The solution is:

	1	9		5	9	8	1		5	
				4	3	1	0	7		
		2	9	7	2		5	2	3	1
5	6	6				6	9	8		
							4		2	7
		8		7	1	0		6		
8		9	2		5			7	4	
		6	4	0		7	5	0		5
8		5		4	3	8				
2		1	0	6	1	6	7			

Further Extensions

- Puzzles may use rooms of different sizes within the same grid.
- The symbol sets are not limited to numbers: letters or other sequences may also be used.
- Grids and rooms may be irregular in shape, not just rectangular.
- Some cells may be designated as forbidden (black cells), similar to crossword puzzles.
- In some puzzles, erroneous entries may also appear. In such cases, the puzzle has no valid solution until the incorrect symbols are removed.

Keywords

Logic puzzle · Recreational mathematics · Grid partitioning · Room shapes · Ghosted Rooms

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